

EXPLORING THE PERCEPTION ON ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR INDUSTRIAL OPERATIONS FROM STUDENTS OF AHMADU BELLO UNIVERSITY, ZARIA

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Abstract

This study explores the perception on adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for industrial operations from students at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. The study achieved the objectives of finding out the perceived role of AI on industrial operations, investigating the perceived benefits of AI on industrial operations and exploring the respondents' concern about the use of AI for industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. A survey research design was adopted using a structured questionnaire by selecting 401 students through random sampling. The findings reveal that majority of the respondents constituting 60.35% reported that AI has positive role in industrial operations. From the respondents, majority of them constituting 69.2 % reported that AI improved efficiency and productivity and most of them also, constituting 56.1%, reported that dependence on technology is a major concern regarding AI use in industrial operations. It is concluded that adoption of AI facilitates industrial operations. It is recommended that integrating AI literacy into the university curriculum, developing strategic partnerships with industry and advocating for national AI education policy, shall be carried out.

Keywords: Adoption, Ahmadu Bello University, Artificial Intelligence, Industrial Operations Students, Zaria

Background

In the 21st century, the most transformative technology that is reshaping markets, economic structures, and social interactions across the world is artificial intelligence (Nwadiani, 2025).

AI integration into workplaces has increased efficiency and has also raised questions about the

future of employment. AI systems can carry out pattern recognition, natural language processing, and complex decision-making with ease. Tasks that were traditionally performed using human cognition. This has increased concerns surrounding technological unemployment across different fields (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2019). Research from advanced economies such as the United Kingdom and the United States of America shows that both the effect of automation on the displacement of labour and a job creation mechanism from innovation in technology (Autor & Salomons, 2018). According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019), 14% of jobs in member countries are at risk of automation, and 32% of roles will experience transformation, emphasising the need for workforce upskilling. However, most of the research conducted on the impact of AI and industrial operations was conducted in industrialised nations, leaving gaps in understanding how it will impact developing economies (Asghar et al., 2025).

Nigeria, the most populous African nation with the largest African economy, presents a good case study to examine. A nation struggling with a fragile labour workforce and a high unemployment rate is now facing another challenge of harnessing AI potential for economic growth (Nwadiani, 2025). In the context of Nigeria, higher educational institutions serve as an excellent study area to understand how the next generation of workforce perceives and prepares for AI transformation.

Established in 1962, Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Zaria is one of Nigeria's largest universities with students from diverse ethnic and socioeconomic backgrounds (Ahmadu Bello University, 2024). The ABU students' perception of AI will offer insights into how the educated Nigerian youth perceive the opportunities and threats presented by AI. The research contributes to the growing body of literature on AI perception in developing economies, providing evidence-based recommendations for workforce development policy in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

AI technology is revolutionizing multiple sectors by enhancing decision making and problem-solving. While AI adoption can potentially improve productivity, it also concerns about job displacement. The transformative impact of AI could change industrial operations and workforce. Contextually, there is no knowledge on adoption of Artificial Intelligence regarding industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Hence, the reason for this study. The study set to fill this gap by exploring the perception on adoption of Artificial Intelligence for industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of this study:

1. To find out the perceived role of AI on industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
2. To investigate the perceived benefits of AI on industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
3. To explore the respondents' concern about the use of AI for industrial operations from students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Literature Review

This section presents the review of related literature used in this study. The review is carried out in line with the objectives of this study. It is presented as follows:

Perceived Role of Artificial Intelligence on Industrial Operations

The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into industrial activities is widely recognized as a driving force behind enhanced efficiency, productivity, and decision-making. AI technologies play a crucial role in streamlining industrial processes. For example, Kumar et al. (2023) note that AI-powered predictive maintenance minimizes equipment downtime and extends machinery lifespan, thereby boosting overall performance. Likewise, Zhang and Lee

(2024) observe that AI applications in supply chain management strengthen coordination, improve demand forecasting, and optimize inventory control, resulting in more resilient systems. Within developing economies, Adeyemi et al. (2025) contend that the adoption of AI increasingly supports industries through real-time monitoring and more effective resource allocation.

Perceived Benefits of Artificial Intelligence on Industrial Operations

AI-driven systems surpass traditional industrial approaches by delivering greater accuracy, speed, and flexibility. Unlike conventional methods that depend largely on manual intervention and fixed rules, AI facilitates adaptive decision-making based on data insights. Smith and Rao (2023) emphasize that AI-based decision-support tools lower human error and enhance production precision, thereby improving operational efficiency. Similarly, Chen et al. (2025) find that organizations implementing AI for process optimization achieve better performance outcomes than those relying on traditional systems. Moreover, Bello and Hassan (2026) present evidence from African manufacturing settings, demonstrating that AI integration enhances product quality and shortens production cycles. This indicates that AI not only strengthens operational performance but also offers a competitive edge over traditional techniques.

Artificial Intelligence Use Concern for Industrial Operations

Beyond improving efficiency, AI reshapes organizational priorities by advancing digital innovation and technological progress. García et al. (2024) assert that the adoption of AI stimulates greater investment in digital infrastructure, encouraging industries to move toward more advanced technological systems. In the same vein, Okonkwo et al. (2025) find that implementing AI in industrial settings gradually replaces manual tasks with automated and intelligent processes. Additionally, Brown and Singh (2026) highlight that AI promotes a

culture of ongoing technological learning and adaptation among employees, reinforcing the shift toward innovation-focused operations. This evolution illustrates how AI transforms industrial mindsets, prompting stakeholders to favor technological solutions over conventional methods.

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted with a structured questionnaire. The population comprised the undergraduate students enrolled at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, during the 2024 academic session with an estimated number of 15,000 students. The samples were 401 students selected through random sampling. Factors such as statistical power, time and resource constraints were considered in determining the sample size. Questionnaire was administered physically to students within two (2) weeks. Information about the study was provided to respondents, consent was duly obtained from respondents. Data obtained was treated with strict confidentiality. Descriptive statistics was used to compute the demographic data as well as that used for the objectives.

Data Presentation

This section presents the data analysed in this study. It is presented in line with the objectives of this study as follows:

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

S/N	Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age	18-24	285	71.07
		25-34	116	28.93
2.	Gender	Male	246	61.35
		Female	155	38.65

Table 2: Perceived Role of AI, Perceived Benefits of AI and AI Use Concerns

S/N	Perceived Role, Benefits and Concerns	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
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1. Perceived Role of AI	Positive	242	60.35
	Negative	20	4.99
	Neutral	124	30.92
	Unsure	15	3.74
<i>Multiple response</i>			
2. Perceived Benefits of AI	Improved efficiency and productivity	277	69.2
	Better quality of life	68	16.9
	Creation of new job opportunities	37	9.2
	Enhanced decision-making	104	25.9
<i>Multiple response</i>			
3. Respondents' Concern about AI Use	Job displacement	127	31.6
	Privacy issues	67	16.6
	Ethical implications	53	13.2
	Dependence on technology	226	56.1

Discussion of the Findings

This section presents the discussion of the findings of this study. It is presented in line with the objectives of this study as follows:

Age Distribution

This section presents the age distribution of the respondents. It reveals a clear concentration of respondents in the 18–24 age group (71.07%), compared with those aged 25–34 (28.93%). This means that the results predominantly capture early adults who were highly digitally engaged and more frequently exposed to artificial intelligence technologies regarding their application in industrial operations. Younger individuals typically report higher performance expectancy and stronger behavioral intentions toward AI tools (Wolfe et al., 2025). In a similar vein, age plays a significant role in AI engagement, with younger people more inclined to experiment with generative AI in both academic and professional settings (Marmolejo-Ramos et al., 2026). Nevertheless, there is growing AI adoption among older professionals when adequate organizational support is available (Cummings-Koether et al., 2025). The implication is that

the generally positive orientation toward AI observed in this study is likely influenced by the dominance of younger respondents, potentially leading to an overestimation of acceptance levels in the broader population, especially among older adults who often report greater uncertainty and lower levels of AI use.

Gender of the Respondents

The analysis on gender indicates that the sample is predominantly male (61.35% compared to 38.65% female), indicating that perceptions on AI regarding its use in industrial operations reflect underlying gender differences in technology use and engagement. Men generally report higher confidence, stronger perceptions of usefulness, and more frequent use of AI systems, whereas women tend to express greater uncertainty and perceive higher risks (Wolfe et al., 2025). In academic contexts, women are also more likely to raise concerns about ethical issues, particularly algorithmic bias and data privacy (Kalim et al., 2025). Additionally, although women are equally exposed to automation-related risks, they tend to adopt AI tools at lower rates, largely due to confidence gaps and less inclusive digital environments. This means that the relatively positive perceptions of AI in this study may be partly shaped by the overrepresentation of male respondents, while a more balanced gender distribution could reveal stronger concerns around ethics, privacy, and employment implications.

Perceived Role of AI on Industrial Operations

The analysis here shows that 60.35% of respondents view AI positively, making it the most common response, while 30.92% remain neutral, 4.99% express negative views, and 3.74% are unsure. There is dominance of positive attitudes toward AI among users with direct experience, particularly as exposure increases. Attitudes toward AI become more favorable with hands-on use, as familiarity reduces uncertainty and fosters “calibrated trust” in system capabilities (Cummings-Koether et al., 2025). Likewise, Perceived usefulness and performance

benefits are key determinants of positive attitudes toward AI adoption (Liu et al., 2025). At the same time, the relatively large neutral segment aligns with recent evidence suggesting that many users still possess only a superficial understanding of AI despite frequent exposure, resulting in mixed or underdeveloped attitudes (Marmolejo-Ramos et al., 2026). This means although AI is generally accepted, this acceptance is often experience-driven and not fully informed, highlighting the need for stronger AI literacy to support more stable and informed adoption regarding its use for industrial operations.

Perceived Benefits of AI on Industrial Operations

This section indicates that the most frequently identified benefit of AI use in industrial operations is increased efficiency and productivity (69.2%), followed by improved decision-making (25.9%), enhanced quality of life (16.9%), and job creation (9.2%). Both organizations and individuals primarily value AI for automating routine tasks and improving productivity (Liu et al., 2025). Similarly, users mainly adopt these tools to streamline workflows and reduce cognitive effort, rather than to generate new employment opportunities (Pitts & Motamedi, 2026). However, AI's impact on labour markets is more nuanced, with job transformation occurring more frequently than direct job creation or job loss (Wolfe et al., 2025). This reveals that respondents in this study largely interpret AI through a productivity-focused perspective, potentially underestimating its wider structural effects, including job redesign, reskilling, and the emergence of hybrid human–AI roles.

Respondents' Concern about the Use of AI for Industrial Operations

Here, the analysis reveals that the leading concern identified regarding AI use in industrial operations is technological dependence (56.1%), followed by job displacement (31.6%), privacy issues (16.6%), and ethical considerations (13.2%). Concerns about job displacement remain widely documented, consistent with global evidence showing that while automation

often transforms rather than eliminates jobs, it still generates significant uncertainty among workers (Marmolejo-Ramos et al., 2026). Privacy concerns also reflect growing evidence that expanded AI use introduces serious data governance and surveillance challenges, particularly in consumer-oriented applications (Kalim et al., 2025). Although ethical concerns appear less frequently, they reflect ongoing global discussions surrounding fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI systems. This indicates that respondents demonstrate a pattern of “cautious acceptance,” where strong perceived benefits coexist with substantial concerns about long-term dependence, employment disruption, and data security.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that students generally hold a positive perception of integrating AI into industrial operations. They recognized its ability to improve efficiency, productivity, and decision-making. However, concerns remain, particularly regarding overreliance on technology and potential job loss. This indicates that while students are receptive to AI adoption, careful planning, guidance, and support are essential to mitigate risks and ensure successful implementation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are provided:

1. The management of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, should host seminars and workshops to enhance students’ knowledge of AI in industrial operations, emphasizing its strategic importance and fostering confidence in its use.
2. The university should promote partnerships with industry to present practical AI projects that demonstrate gains in efficiency, productivity, and decision-making, helping students better appreciate the advantages of AI.

3. University management should develop policies and programs to tackle students' concerns, including ethical AI practices, privacy education, and skill-building initiatives, equipping students to engage responsibly in an AI-driven world.

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